

REPRESENTATION OF GENDER ROLES IN THE UŞAK FOLKTALE**“HAZRETI SÜLEYMAN AND THE ZÜMRÜDÜANKA”****Derya OZCAN GULER¹, Mehmet GOKDOGAN²****¹ Assoc. Prof. Dr. Uşak University, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences,
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Folktales are significant cultural tools that function as carriers of collective memory and play a vital role in shaping individuals' identities and social roles. Although femininity and masculinity are often presented as fixed and immutable categories, these roles—independent of biological sex—are continually constructed and reproduced by society. Gender is not an innate attribute but a performance constructed through culturally repetitive practices. In this context, folktales are not merely entertaining narratives; they are critical mediums for understanding how gender identities are shaped and transmitted across generations. This study examines the folktale “*Hazreti Süleyman and the Zümrüdüanka*”, collected from the Uşak region, within the framework of the construction and transmission of gender roles. Employing a thematic analysis approach, one of the qualitative research methods, the study conducts a detailed examination of the narrative structure and character representations to explore how gender roles are discursively constructed and reinforced. Findings indicate that the female figure in the tale is associated with specific roles and expectations, and these roles are normalized through repetition within the narrative, thus contributing to the reinforcement of gender norms. The study concludes that folktales exert a covert yet influential role in shaping individuals' gender identities. In “*Hazreti Süleyman and the Zümrüdüanka*”, the presentation of gender roles in fixed patterns leads to their unquestioned internalization by individuals. However, based on the assumption that social norms are dynamic and fluid, it is also emphasized that the inherent flexibility of the folktale genre allows space for transformation and reinterpretation of these roles. Therefore, folktales are evaluated as a cultural medium in which gender roles are not only reproduced but also redefined and reconstructed. The evolving nature of folktales in response to changing societal expectations underscores the fact that gender roles are not static, but rather subject to continuous redefinition.

Keywords: Femininity, Folktale, Thematic Analysis Method, Gender, Uşak Tale

“HAZRETİ SÜLEYMAN İLE ZÜMRÜDÜANKA” ADLI UŞAK MASALINDA TOPLUMSAL CİNSİYET ROLLERİNİN TEMSİLİ

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ÖZET

Masallar, toplumsal hafızanın taşıyıcıları olarak bireylerin kimliklerini ve toplumsal rollerini şekillendiren önemli araçlardır. Kadınlık ve erkeklik, çoğu zaman sabit ve değişmez kategoriler olarak sunulsa da biyolojik cinsiyetlerden bağımsız olarak bu roller, toplum tarafından sürekli olarak yeniden üretilen ve kurgulanan kimliklerdir. Toplumsal cinsiyet, doğuştan gelen bir özellik değil, kültürel pratiklerle tekrar eden bir süreç içerisinde inşa edilen bir performans olarak değerlendirilebilir. Bu bağlamda, masallar sadece eğlenceli anlatılar olmanın ötesinde, cinsiyet kimliklerinin nasıl biçimlendirildiğini ve aktarılmaya devam ettiğini anlamak açısından önemli bir inceleme alanıdır. Bu çalışmada, Uşak yöresinden derlenen “*Hazreti Süleyman İle Zümrüdüanka*” adlı masal, toplumsal cinsiyet rollerinin kurgulanışı ve aktarımı bağlamında incelenmiştir. Çalışmada, nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden tematik inceleme yöntemi kullanılarak masalın karakterleri ve olay örgüsü detaylı bir şekilde analiz edilmiş, toplumsal cinsiyet rollerinin söylemsel olarak nasıl inşa edildiği ve pekiştirildiği araştırılmıştır. Masalda yer alan kadın figürünün belirli roller ve beklentilerle ilişkilendirildiği, bu rolün sürekli tekrarlanarak toplumsal düzende norm hâline getirildiği tespit edilmiştir. Masalların, bireylerin cinsiyet kimliklerini oluşturmada örtük bir şekilde etkili olduğu sonucuna ulaşılmıştır. “*Hazreti Süleyman İle Zümrüdüanka*” masalında, toplumsal cinsiyet rollerinin sabit kalıplar içerisinde sunulması, bireylerin bu rolleri sorgulamaksızın benimsemesine yol açmaktadır. Ancak toplumsal normların değişken ve akışkan bir yapıya sahip olduğu gerçeğinden hareketle, masal türünün dinamik yapısının bu rollerin dönüşümüne de olanak tanıdığı belirtilmiştir. Masal türü, toplumsal cinsiyet rollerinin hem yeniden üretildiği hem de dönüştürülüp yeniden kurgulanabildiği bir kültürel alan olarak değerlendirilmiştir. Masalların zamanla değişen toplumsal beklentilere paralel olarak dönüşmesi, toplumsal cinsiyet rollerinin sabit değil, sürekli olarak yeniden tanımlanan yapılar olduğuna işaret etmektedir.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Kadınlık, Masal, Tematik İnceleme Yöntemi, Toplumsal Cinsiyet, Uşak Masalı.

Introduction

Fairy tales are among the most significant carriers of a society's collective memory and cultural heritage, transmitted from generation to generation. These oral and written narratives, which have persisted through time by evolving and enriching themselves, not only reflect the cultural imprints of the communities in which they emerged but also serve as powerful tools in transmitting these traces to future generations and different societies. Fairy tales simultaneously embody universal human traits and the unique cultural richness of individual societies.

An examination of the variants of fairy tales reveals that, while they may possess universal narrative qualities, they frequently exhibit characteristics specific to local cultures and reflect the social identity of the community. Therefore, fairy tales can also be viewed as reflections of individuals' unconscious worlds (Özcan & Erdik, 2021: 287).

“The tradition of oral storytelling and its products—including myths, fairy tales, epics, and folk narratives in any form—reflect the worldview of the society to which they belong” (Duman, 2022: 16). Accordingly, oral literature should not be considered merely an aesthetic form of expression, but also as a medium in which social norms and values are reproduced. These narrative products act as carriers of cultural memory and play a key role in the socialization process of individuals, contributing significantly to the construction of cultural identities.

In Turkish folk narratives, the heroes' journeys often involve confronting either external enemies or internal struggles, which highlights both the personal and social dimensions of these stories. Originating in oral tradition, Turkish folktales have since been transferred to written sources and now represent a fundamental component of Turkish literature. These tales are not merely sources of entertainment; rather, they serve as vehicles of cultural heritage that transmit moral teachings and social codes. Anatolia's rich cultural fabric and its historical role as a host to numerous civilizations have diversified and deepened the content of these tales, endowing them with a more universal dimension that transcends regional boundaries.

Given the influence of fairy tales in shaping the attitudes and behaviors of both individuals and societies, it is evident that they also play an essential role in constructing gender roles. Characters in these narratives—often gods, demigods, or humans endowed with extraordinary traits—mirror the ideals and norms of the communities they belong to (Gökdoğan, 2019: 336). In this regard, fairy tales in the Turkish cultural universe emerge as

powerful narrative tools that simultaneously convey individual experiences and reproduce social norms for future generations.

Numerous studies have shown that fairy tales significantly contribute to the construction and reinforcement of gender roles. The ways in which femininity and masculinity are portrayed in these tales have a profound effect on how children perceive and internalize these roles.

In this study, the folktale titled “*Hazreti Süleyman and the Zümürdüanka*”, collected from the Uşak region and introduced into academic literature by the author, is examined through a critical lens focused on gender roles. The analysis involves the investigation of characters’ roles, their inner journeys, and the social messages embedded in the narrative. The aim is to explore how gender perceptions are formed, reinforced, or challenged, and how fairy tales function as role models influencing individual identity formation.

Purpose, Scope, and Methodology of the Study

This study aims to examine the representation of gender roles and their impact on the world of meaning in the folktale “*Hazreti Süleyman and the Zümürdüanka*”, which was collected from the Uşak region. The research seeks to reveal how gender perceptions are constructed and how these perceptions are conveyed through the female characters in the narrative. Moreover, it investigates how the gender roles in the tale align with traditional viewpoints and explores their implications for the concepts of social equality and justice.

Within the scope of this study, the folktale is analyzed through the lens of gender representation, focusing on how the social roles of the characters are constructed and how these roles conform to broader societal norms. Special attention is given to the ways in which characters are portrayed from a gender perspective and how traditional characteristics are reflected throughout the tale. Based on the data obtained from the narrative, a textual analysis is conducted on the representation of gender, and the implications of these representations for gender equality are critically discussed. The study also assesses the tale’s gender portrayals in relation to the broader concepts of gender justice and social equity, offering insight into how fairy tales reinforce gender norms and influence social structures.

The study adopts the thematic analysis method, one of the qualitative research approaches, which is characterized as “a process that involves examining perceptions and events in their natural context with a realistic and holistic perspective through qualitative data collection methods such as observation, interviews, and document analysis” (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2021: 18).

Thematic analysis is a data analysis technique grounded in the identification of recurring patterns (themes) within the data. It involves an active process of reflexivity and interpretation, wherein the researcher becomes directly involved in the analytical process. Although not an independent research methodology in itself, thematic analysis is widely applied within qualitative research frameworks to define, examine, and interpret meaningful patterns embedded in textual or observational data (Braun & Clarke, 2006: 79). Through this method, the researcher interprets the collected data in light of their own knowledge and experience, engaging as an active participant in the construction of meaning throughout the research process.

1. Theoretical Framework of Gender

Gender, beyond the notion of biological sex, is a social construct that defines the roles, responsibilities, and expectations assigned to individuals within a society. Far from being merely a biological category, gender is a historically, culturally, and politically shaped structure. Judith Butler (2019: 25) argues that gender is not an innate identity but a “performative” phenomenon constructed through social interactions and cultural norms. This approach highlights that gender is not a fixed biological condition but a structural process constantly reproduced through social relations and daily practices. Similarly, Joan Scott (2007: 49) defines gender as a reflection of cultural and historical structures, emphasizing its role in shaping power dynamics and influencing societal structures.

Gender, therefore, is not simply a biological determinant but a dynamic process that helps explain how identities such as femininity and masculinity are constructed, transmitted, and transformed in specific social and cultural contexts. It not only informs personal identities but also structures societal norms, power relations, and systems of inequality. West and Zimmerman (1987: 125) define gender as a phenomenon that is continuously constructed through individuals’ social interactions and practices. This perspective allows for a deeper understanding of the variability of gender and the ways in which social norms are reshaped through transformations in social relationships. Accordingly, gender is something that is continuously “done” and “reconstructed” through individual behavior, interpersonal engagement, and social participation—making it a fluid and contextually situated process.

Societies assign different roles to men and women, thereby distinguishing responsibilities and expectations based on gender. Women are typically expected to be responsible for domestic labor, while men are assigned the duty of meeting the economic needs of the family. This traditional division of labor reflects how gender norms are internalized and how individuals are shaped by these expectations.

Many studies have demonstrated that fairy tales play a critical role in transmitting gender roles and shaping their influence on individuals. The portrayal of femininity in such narratives serves as a powerful influence, particularly on how children perceive and internalize gender roles.

Fairy tales are cultural structures that include elements of both individual and collective interaction and are shaped by elements of the fantastic and the extraordinary. At their core, fairy tales are situated at the intersection of subjectivity (individual identity) and anonymity (collective values), which allows for the interweaving of societal norms and personal interpretation. Considering fairy tales as a process of interaction at both the individual and social levels enables a more nuanced reflection on how cultural structures and social norms shape individual perceptions. They serve as powerful tools for examining the dynamics between personal subjectivity and societal objectivity, revealing how gender perceptions are constructed and transformed into social norms over time.

Scott (1986: 1067) asserts that gender is “not a thing but a process,” emphasizing its transformative capacity and its role in shaping social structures. This perspective provides valuable insight into how representations of gender in fairy tales may evolve over time.

Fairy tales not only influence individual perceptions of gender roles but also powerfully reinforce social norms. In this regard, they function as social instruments that define and normalize femininity, playing a formative role in the development of social identities. Butler’s (1990: 25) concept of gender performativity reinforces the view that fairy tales exert a strong influence on the construction of gender roles. In childhood especially, these tales shape the foundation of gendered social identities. The depictions of femininity they present illustrate how societal norms are internalized and sustained.

The concept of gender refers to the culturally constructed roles and relational networks assigned to men and women; however, with the rise of gender studies and its popularization through feminist scholarship, the field has initially focused predominantly on women (Güler, 2023: 1). Gender studies thus originally sought to reveal the structural inequalities and discrimination experienced by women in society. Over time, however, the concept of gender has evolved into a broader analytical framework that also encompasses the roles, expectations, and social implications affecting men and other gender identities.

Gender should not be understood as a fixed or static concept but as an ever-changing and evolving process (Scott, 1986: 1067). Scott’s emphasis on the fluidity of gender is especially useful in understanding the transformative impact of fairy tales on social norms. This transformation invites inquiry into how fairy tales adapt to different cultural contexts

over time and how these contexts influence gender perceptions. Fairy tales reflect the values of their time and place, while simultaneously shaping them.

In this process of change and transformation, fairy tales influence both society and the individual. Since the cultural codes embedded in tales reflect gender ideologies, they act as agents in shaping social direction. Consequently, fairy tales clearly demonstrate that gender is a multilayered and dynamic process. The dynamic perspective of West and Zimmerman (1987: 125) supports this view by highlighting that gender must be understood as a fluid, interactional phenomenon. As cultural reflections, fairy tales illustrate the variability of gender and how this variability is absorbed into and disseminated by social norms. This multilayered interaction offers a crucial lens through which to interpret the role of fairy tales in broader processes of social transformation.

The interpersonal dynamics present in fairy tales enhance their capacity to transmit gender-related values and reinforce dominant gender ideologies. As carriers of cultural codes and embedded knowledge, fairy tales also reveal how perceptions of social identity may be transformed into stereotypes over time. This process illuminates how the ideological function of fairy tales ensures the continuity of gendered expectations.

2. Gender Representations in the Tale of Hazreti Süleyman and the Zümrüdüanka

The representations of gender roles will be examined in the context of gender themes found in the tale of Hazreti Süleyman ile Zümrüdüanka. During the thematic analysis process, meaning patterns will be created using data that may serve as evidence of gender inequality within the tale. The social roles of the tale's characters and how these roles are reflected in their gender identities will be analyzed in detail, focusing on how gender roles are reinforced, transformed, or reconstructed in tales.

"Hazreti Süleyman said to the Zümrüdüanka bird: 'Are you going to undo what God has written?'"

The dialogue between Hazreti Süleyman and the Zümrüdüanka bird is a significant narrative emphasizing the immutability of divine will. It reveals how gender roles are linked to the concept of destiny. Male authority and the unchallengeable nature of divine fate are presented as the foundational elements that sustain the patriarchal order. Hazreti Süleyman is viewed in sacred texts as a symbol of wisdom and justice, while Zümrüdüanka is depicted in mythology as a unique being associated with rebirth and transformation. This dialogue

illustrates a scene where a traditional authority figure (Hazreti Süleyman) represents divine order and questions another being's (Zümrüdüanka's) will.

The effort of Zümrüdüanka to defy this destiny symbolizes a woman's questioning of social norms through her individual will. However, this effort is deemed "inappropriate" by the male figure who represents divine authority. (Connell, 2005: 45) examined how patriarchal structures produce and reproduce gender roles and emphasized that attempts by individuals to challenge these norms are often suppressed. Here, Zümrüdüanka's questioning of fate represents a context where resistance to patriarchal norms is limited.

Hazreti Süleyman's association of Zümrüdüanka's action with defiance against divine fate demonstrates how gender roles are legitimized through the concept of destiny. In this context, the identification of male authority with divine order underscores the unquestionability and continuity of patriarchal structures. Zümrüdüanka's attempt to challenge fate symbolizes the effort to transcend individual will and social norms, and its designation as "inappropriate" indicates the suppression of women's resistance to patriarchal order.

Zümrüdüanka's act represents not only a pursuit of personal freedom but also an attempt to transcend the fixed boundaries of gender roles. However, this effort is rejected by the male figure representing authority, reinforcing the message that women must submit to social norms. This highlights the structural mechanisms that restrict the questioning of the patriarchal order.

Those who attempt to challenge authority, especially women, have often been accused of "disrupting the natural order." However, like Zümrüdüanka, gender roles have undergone change and been reshaped throughout history. In this context, it is possible to reinterpret this narrative not only as a matter of fate but also in terms of social transformation and authority relations.

"Zümrüdüanka immediately took the girl and brought her to an unknown place in an unknown land."

In narratives, turning points of fate sometimes appear unexpectedly. A sudden force disrupts the established order and drives the protagonist into the unknown. In the tale, Zümrüdüanka's act of taking the girl to an unfamiliar place symbolizes women being directed by forces beyond their will. In traditional narratives, female characters are often portrayed as passive; their destinies are determined by a male figure or a supernatural force. In this scene, the girl cannot make her own decision; her future is decided by Zümrüdüanka, a mythological

authority figure. This scene metaphorically represents the control imposed on women's lives from early childhood. Some sacred places are believed to be associated with divine power due to the events, natural phenomena, or spiritual experiences that occur there. It is also believed that divine signs and inspirations are necessary to determine the sanctity of such places (Kayacan, 2021: 803). The girl's transportation to an "unknown place" symbolizes how, in patriarchal societies, women are distanced from their points of origin and reshaped according to social norms. This reflects how gender excludes women's subjectivity and repositions them within social structures.

Although Zümrüdüanka is often associated with wisdom and rebirth, in this tale, it gains a different meaning as a figure that takes the girl away. If Zümrüdüanka is considered a savior, the narrative might reflect a traditional story of rescuing and protecting a woman from danger. However, if the destination and reason remain unclear, this may also suggest that the woman's fate is determined by a male-dominated or authoritarian power. Regarding this issue, (Dökmen, 2019: 54) notes that gender roles are internalized through social norms from early childhood. Here, Zümrüdüanka appears as a patriarchal agent directing the girl's shaping process. In this context, the girl being taken to an unknown place by Zümrüdüanka symbolizes the control and shaping of women's lives from childhood. This reflects the process of reshaping women according to social norms and distancing them from subjectivity. Her removal to an "unknown place" represents her detachment from identity and freedom and her repositioning according to the demands of social structures. This process reflects the patriarchal order as a force that suppresses women's individuality and legitimizes control over them. Thus, the tale clearly expresses the control and objectification faced by women while being shaped to conform to social norms. It demonstrates that their destinies are often determined independently of their own will, rendering them invisible, passive, and restricted within society.

"The girl said: 'Can you see that horse? Cut open its belly. Get inside it. Don't make a sound.'"

Tales often present magical worlds with hidden meanings behind ordinary objects and beings. For heroes to survive, transform, or pass a test, extraordinary solutions are often required, and these narratives are woven with deep symbols. The female character's suggestion in the tale reveals her rational and solution-oriented role. The girl does not act directly, but she serves as a guiding figure through her knowledge. She appears as the one

who sets the male character (or another subject in the narrative) into motion for salvation. This supports the theme of intuitive female wisdom seen in many folk narratives.

Women are often portrayed not as direct combatants but as figures who resolve issues through intelligence, strategy, and patience. This tale can be interpreted as an example showing that women survive and direct situations not by exerting overt power but through indirect means. Especially in patriarchal societies, women have sustained their existence by avoiding direct conflict or devising strategic solutions. In this case, the girl suggests a method of hiding and protection rather than engaging in direct conflict. However, combining the solution with silence implies that the woman must be defined by "compliance" and "obedience." Although the female character seems to create a unique space based on the condition of taking a subjective role, this space remains restricted by the patriarchal structure. Regarding this issue, (Fine, 2010: 68) emphasizes that gender norms restrict women's behavior to be both autonomous and compliant. The emphasis on silence and passivity by the girl here reveals how patriarchal structures impose adherence to expected behavioral patterns.

While the female character's suggestion indicates her rarely seen rational and solution-oriented role in tales, the limitation of this role by silence and compliance is noteworthy. Though her strategic solution to eliminate danger signals autonomy and competence, its combination with the demand for silence shows that this competence is kept under control within patriarchal norms. A woman's autonomous actions are accepted only when they align with social expectations. Thus, framing the suggestion with passivity and compliance sets boundaries on women's ability to express individuality within social structures. Consequently, the tale reveals how patriarchal norms infiltrate the narrative, requiring women to be both rational and obedient.

"Zümrüdüanka returned to the nest and saw the girl and the boy sitting hand in hand, knee to knee."

Tales do not merely depict magical beings and extraordinary events; they also reflect social norms, moral values, and assumptions about relationships. In the tale, the image of the girl and the boy sitting hand in hand, knee to knee implies emotional closeness or romance. However, since this scene is observed by Zümrüdüanka, a third-party overseeing perspective is introduced. This signifies that in social structures, particularly in traditional societies, male-female relationships are closely monitored, and intimacy is evaluated within socially defined frameworks rather than as a private domain. This can be read as an example emphasizing that individuals must act according to social perspectives in their relationships. Zümrüdüanka's

observation symbolizes the surveillance of social authority and moral values. Moreover, the union of the male and female characters represents the validation of gender norms through the concept of "destiny." This reflects an attempt by social structures to reproduce the "ideal family" model. The "happy ending" narrative often seen in tales reflects a structure based on the acceptance and internalization of traditional gender roles imposed by the patriarchal order. (Ölçer Özünel, 2006: 112) notes that the "happy ending" motifs in tales generally reinforce gender roles. The union of the male and female characters should be viewed as a norm ensuring the continuity of the male-dominated structure. It symbolizes the legitimization of gender norms through destiny and the reproduction of the idealized form of togetherness within the patriarchal system. In such narratives, the concept of a "happy ending" conveys the message that social order must be maintained through the adoption of traditional gender roles by men and women. The act of the girl and boy sitting together does not represent individual desires but rather a union dictated by social norms and expectations. This results in the female character becoming a "completed" figure not through her independence but by being positioned alongside the male. Thus, the tale reinforces the ideal family model imposed by the social structure and strengthens the notion that the relationship between men and women must be arranged within this normative framework.

"Zümrüdüanka was never seen by humankind again."

One of the most striking aspects of tales is when magical beings withdraw from the stage, leaving humans to chart their own destinies. The disappearance of such mystical figures sometimes signifies the completion of their wisdom or the unworthiness of humanity. This ending indicates the failure of individual will to challenge social norms. Zümrüdüanka's disappearance emphasizes how the patriarchal system silences individual resistance. It shows the continuity of gender roles as a structural tool of oppression. (Butler, 1990: 85) draws attention to the performativity of gender and states that individual resistance is often neutralized by social structures. This ending in the tale reveals the limited effect of challenging the patriarchal order.

Zümrüdüanka's disappearance symbolizes the invisibility and exclusion experienced by women under the pressure of social structures. Though active throughout the tale, Zümrüdüanka is ultimately suppressed by the system and removed from the social sphere. This demonstrates how women's efforts to question and transcend social norms are silenced and how their inclusion in the system is hindered. Her withdrawal from the narrative reflects how women are rendered invisible when they try to exist as autonomous subjects. The tale

reveals gender roles as a force limiting women's freedom and excluding them from the system.

Overall, the tale reflects traditional narrative patterns of female representation in the context of gender. The female character's fate is determined from birth, shaped not by her own will but by external forces. Her societal placement is defined within the boundaries drawn by male authority rather than individual autonomy. This reflects a patriarchal structure where meaning is derived not from women's personal identity but from their social roles.

Throughout the tale, the female character is portrayed as someone who must be protected and controlled. This reveals that women are positioned not as independent subjects but as beings in need of protection under male authority. Those who exercise authority over her life function as representatives of the patriarchal order, from divine figures to supernatural beings. In this context, the woman does not exist as an individual subject in social life but as a figure directed by others, and thus male domination becomes the primary dynamic shaping her existence.

The tale's narrative structure reinforces the belief that a woman should fulfill a role deemed suitable within the male-dominated world, rather than expressing her freedom and individuality. There is no emphasis on her personal development; instead, her life is constructed as a process completed by uniting with a man. At the end of the tale, the fulfillment of a fate determined by the patriarchal order ensures the union of the male and female characters, and a narrative of completion through marriage and love is constructed rather than one of individual subjectivity.

In conclusion, the tale's fictional structure reveals that the woman's identity is shaped by roles defined within the framework of gender norms. A narrative is constructed not around the woman's individuality but around her social role in the male world. Thus, the tale can be evaluated as a narrative that reinforces traditional gender roles and ensures the continuity of the patriarchal order. Additionally, the woman's destiny is often determined by male authority figures or supernatural forces. The female character's ineffectiveness in decision-making processes positions her as a passive subject, while the male is frequently depicted as the savior, guide, or figure of power. Throughout the tale, the woman's ability to act independently is restricted, and her identity is shaped primarily through the guidance or intervention of others. This reflects traditional narrative patterns that highlight the roles assigned to women by society rather than their individual existence. Therefore, the tale not

only reveals social assumptions about male-female relationships but also illustrates how patriarchal structures ensure the continuity of these relationships.

Conclusion

The folktale “*Hazreti Süleyman and the Zümriüanka*” offers a compelling example of how gender is constructed and how female characters are represented within traditional narrative patterns. Throughout the tale, the female protagonist is portrayed as a figure whose destiny is shaped by a predetermined fate from birth—guided not by her own choices, but by external forces. This narrative strategy reflects a traditional mindset in which women are positioned not as autonomous subjects but as passive objects within social structures. Her identity is not formed through individual agency but through the interventions of sacred, mythological, or patriarchal authorities. Her existence is continuously monitored and reshaped within the confines of male-dominated systems.

Although the narrative presents the woman as possessing intellectual or intuitive strength, these abilities are only acknowledged when exercised within the boundaries set by patriarchal structures. The woman is accepted only insofar as she remains compliant, silent, and passive. Even when she assumes the role of a guide or problem-solver, her actions are mediated through indirect means, reinforcing the expectation of unconditional conformity to established norms. The tale repeatedly emphasizes that the woman’s journey—both literal and symbolic—is dependent on the guidance of another, typically male or mythological, figure.

The narrative ultimately implies that the female character attains “completion” only through union with a male counterpart. Her personal growth or subjectivity is not the focus; rather, fulfillment is achieved through romantic partnership, echoing traditional scripts of love and marriage. This reinforces the idea that a woman’s value is determined by how well she conforms to social expectations, and that any desires, preferences, or objections she may have are either suppressed or redirected by higher authorities.

From a broader perspective, the tale does not portray the female character as an independent and autonomous being, but rather as a figure shaped, regulated, and constrained within the limits of patriarchal ideology. Her representation reflects a cultural narrative that naturalizes gender roles, suppresses individuality, and reinforces a socially constructed image of womanhood defined by passivity and dependency. In this context, the tale operates not only as a cultural narrative but also as an ideological instrument that participates in the reproduction of gender norms.

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K.K.1. APAYDIN, Eşe, 85, , okur-yazar, ev hanımı, Mayıs 2024, UŞAK

In-Depth Interview

I.I. 1. APAYDIN, Eşe, 85, literate, housewife, May 2024, Uşak (Turkey).

Folktale – Hazreti Süleyman and Zümrüdüanka

Hazreti Süleyman was one day talking with Zümrüdüanka. During their conversation, he paused and said, “A son has been born to the king of a country from the eastern lands.” Then he continued his conversation. Later, after some time, he paused again and said, “A king from such-and-such land has had a daughter born to him.” He said, “These two will marry in twenty years.” Zümrüdüanka said, “O Süleyman, how is that possible? One is in the east, and the other in the west.” Hazreti Süleyman said to Zümrüdüanka, “Are you going to undo what God has written?” Zümrüdüanka said, “No, but I will prevent it. If I can’t prevent it,” she said, “then I will no longer appear to humankind, I will not go among people,” and she left from there. Zümrüdüanka went to the country where the baby girl was. Her mother had wrapped her in swaddling clothes and laid her in the garden, and during this time went inside for something. As soon as Zümrüdüanka arrived, she snatched the baby girl. She took her straight to an unknown place in an unknown land. Time passed and passed, and of course they grew up. The son of the king from that eastern country was very fond of hunting. He said to his father, “There’s no game left around here that I haven’t hunted; I want to go to other lands and hunt there too.” His father said, “Go, my son, may your path be clear.” While traveling, as they approached an island, a terrible storm broke out. The prince said, “Let’s go ashore on this island. I’ll hunt there, and you can prepare food and drink.” While hunting, he heard a voice from above saying, “You down there, come!” He stopped. He looked to the right—nothing, to the left—nothing. Then he raised his head and saw a girl in a place where a human normally wouldn’t be able to reach. The girl said, “Why don’t you come up?” He said, “I don’t have wings to fly up there. Only those with wings can go up there.” She said, “Do you see that horse? Cut open its belly. Get inside. Don’t make a sound. Soon Zümrüdüanka will come. I will make her bring you up here.” When Zümrüdüanka came, the girl said, “Mother, you always leave me and go. I get so bored like this. Please bring that horse lying down there up to me so I can be friends with it.” That day also happened to be the day Hazreti Süleyman had foretold. Zümrüdüanka immediately grabbed the horse with her talons, lifted it up, and went straight to Prophet Süleyman. She said, “I won.” Hazreti Süleyman said, “No, you didn’t win. You brought up a horse from somewhere, but did you look inside it?” Zümrüdüanka said, “I didn’t look.” Hazreti Süleyman said, “Go look, then come and we’ll talk.” Zümrüdüanka went back to the nest. When she got there, she saw the girl and the boy sitting hand in hand, side by side. Zümrüdüanka never showed herself to humankind again.

SOURCE

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T.C.
UŞAK ÜNİVERSİTESİ
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BİLİMSEL ARAŞTIRMA VE YAYIN ETİĞİ KURULU KARARLARI

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KARAR 2024-69

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